
SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF WORKING WITH DISORDERED YOUTH

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Abstract.

In this article, the problems of directing unorganized youth to the profession that arise in the conditions of globalization are very diverse and comprehensive, unimaginably complex, very urgent and acute at the same time, and the ways to solve them are discussed.

Key words.

globalization, profession, unorganized youth, youth register.

Introduction

Today, we live in a very intense and complex time, which is changing at a rapid pace. Because the 21st century, like other countries, has presented a number of problems that need to be solved. These problems are directly related to young people. Because it is no exaggeration to say that young people are the foundation of tomorrow. The urgency of this issue is connected with the uniqueness of our current era, in a word, we are living in a time when processes called "globalization" are taking place. Therefore, the issue of directing unorganized youth to the profession is now not only national, but also global in nature.

Literature Analysis And Methodology

In this part of our work, we will focus on the problems of youth policy and career orientation of unorganized youth in the context of globalization. Providing the labor market with personnel suitable for modern needs is an important issue for every country. This, in turn, depends on the level of organization of youth vocational training. In order to solve the problem, we need to have an understanding of the youth register. "Youth Register" is a register of unemployed youths between the ages of 18 and 30 who have the need and desire to learn knowledge and skills, as well as socio-legal and psychological support in each sector area. mailing list. In our country, large-scale work is being carried out in the

field of state policy related to youth. In recent years, a special system has been created to support young people in every way, to protect their rights and legal interests, and to educate young people who are able to take responsibility for the future of our country. We have no choice but to admit that only 15% of the population is employed in the organized sector of agriculture, at the same time, most of the agro-industrial enterprises in rural districts have stopped and the level of coverage of the population by this sector is very low. It should be recognized that the shortcomings in the agricultural sector have created a very complex and severe imbalance, that is, the population of the country is forced to spend more than 60 percent of their income on the purchase of food products, which negatively affects the development of other sectors with high labor capacity.

By the end of the 20th century, a completely new historical period began in the fate of our nation. The experience of history shows that, regardless of which period, which country, which system it is in, educating the whole generation into mature people was considered to be the first priority task. Developing the human personality and its high spiritual qualities, forming the national independence ideology, educating the young generation in the spirit of respect for our rich cultural heritage and historical values, and love for our independent homeland is one of the important tasks before all of us. Among the priorities set by the President, working with unorganized youth, studying this layer, and uniting them is one of the urgent problems of today. Who are unorganized youth? How did the unorganized youth layer come about? What kind of society are they? If we focus on one number to find answers to these questions, today the population of Uzbekistan exceeds 32 million, and more than 10 million of them are young people, and almost half of these ten million young people are unorganized youth. Now the question arises, what kind of society are the unorganized youth? Unorganized youth is defined as youth who are not engaged in any profession or in a certain part of education, who do not have higher or secondary specialized education, and who are not provided with a fixed job. In our society the age groups of this layer are 19-24 and 26-30 years old. Young people of the first group are mainly graduates of secondary and special education, they have graduated from colleges and academic lyceums and either apply to higher education institutions, or sign contracts with agencies and organizations working in their field. are accepted, but not all of them stay at work and do not continue it. Only 10% of graduates of academic lyceums and vocational colleges are able to enter the first year of study. The rest of the young people are retrained to continue their studies, while others do not want to

continue their studies and cannot get a job, they are the first group of unorganized youth. The second group of young people did not continue their studies, spent their days here and there through "black labor" in the language of our people, or because they did not have enough skills and qualifications after graduating from higher education institutions. , we can include older youths who are not working in their field, and have not found a "deserving job" in their language, and these are the second group of the unorganized youth layer.

We can see them everywhere now. We must also say that many of them are looking for work abroad because they could not find a suitable job, and to earn money there, they are doing extremely disgusting and vile things. The events that are happening in some countries that we hear on radio and television at the moment are those who have gone abroad to make easy money, or the attempts of evil forces to destroy peace are their empty promises. - the fact that it originates from the same individuals who were deceived, became spiritual prisoners, and could not find their place in society, can be a clear proof that life itself puts this urgent topic in front of us. Now let's think about how the unorganized youth layer is emerging. The main reason for this situation is primarily the low level of parents and the education they give to their children. The old-fashioned way of thinking and backward worldview that some of our people still have is the main factor of this problem. If not, parents should teach their children from a young age, "What do you study and do, rather do work, that's how you'll get enough, and you'll lead the world by studying?" One of the painful points of the issue is that they reluctantly involve the child in "black work" and distract the child from studying under this pretext, and on top of that, they do not teach him a better profession, so to speak, they "burn both the Sikh and the kebab". In solving the problems before us, it is appropriate to look at each and every reason. When a child's young mind was sharp and receptive, instead of directing them to a proper profession or study, they allowed the children to spend their time on the streets, every time they went to school or went to school. There are many parents who fill their pockets with money when they go to winter, give mobile phones and computers to their children, who are still in the stage of formation, and leave them to their own devices without supervision. No child wants to read a book from a young age and does not beg his parents, they are interested in entertainment at this time, but his parents give him the necessary education from a young age, and teach him to study and work. if he directs, he will definitely grow up to be a person who will benefit the society and his family in the future. But instead of that, what can be expected from a child who

has been busy with entertainment and transient things from a young age and grew up surrounded by mobile phones and computers? Because the education given at a young age plays an important role in how a person will grow up in the future. At this point, I found it necessary to mention the following opinion of Abdulla Awlani: "Education is either life or death for us, or salvation or destruction." , it's a matter of either happiness or disaster." Undoubtedly, the family is the real school of life and the center of education. We must instill in the young generation science and profession from a young age, so that when he grows up, he will consciously understand the benefits of this and the correctness of the education given. If we can do this, he will understand the benefits of reading, he will not lift his head from the book, he will not need any computer games or mobile phones. It will not be necessary to force him to study and advise him. In several developed countries, for example, in Japan, such organic education and upbringing are carried out together. Japanese youth prefer reading above all else. In Japan, there are bookshops and book cafes everywhere in subways, avenues, streets, whether it is a big city or a remote village. They don't care about anything else. Attendance in Japanese schools is 99.9%, no student comes to school without a school uniform. The order in science exams is so high that Japanese students don't even imagine helping each other or doing all kinds of tricks, they all work for themselves and their future.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In our opinion, in order to achieve the effectiveness of cultural, educational, and educational activities for unorganized youth and to create in them a sense of confidence in tomorrow, it is necessary to carry out the following activities:

First, to rapidly implement measures aimed at curbing inflation, which is increasing day by day, for this purpose, to expand the scope of material and technical assistance to rural youth, based on marketing research, to increase the scope of material and technical assistance to the rural youth, based on marketing research re-examination of settlement, establishment of multi-level agrarian economy, including complex mechanized state agro-industrial associations specializing in cotton cultivation;

Secondly, to introduce the practice of setting retail prices by limiting the sales mark-up for flour, vegetable oil, laundry soap, which is necessary to meet the daily needs of the population, and in this way, to socially support people, including the unorganized youth;

Thirdly, to strengthen day by day the actions started in order to create an environment of anti-corruption and justice in the fields of education and health

care, law enforcement and to convince the people that they will reach a logical conclusion;

Fourth, to establish economic relations that serve the comprehensive development of all rural areas, rather than consuming limited production resources in a selected district of the regions.

Fifth, study the conditions of colleges from the point of view of the new situation in the field of education and establish branches of industrial enterprises in their appropriate buildings, including enterprises specializing in tailoring, footwear, and furniture production;

CONCLUSION

Indeed, the problems that arise due to this globalization are very diverse and comprehensive, unimaginably complex, and at the same time, very urgent and urgent. In education in Japan, national traditions and the spirit of Japanese education are mixed with education, and the fact that the world's leading specialists are growing up from Japan, the increase of the country's gross domestic product, and most importantly, the low number of unemployed people in society prove how effective the Japanese education system is. I am far from praising or beating anyone with these thoughts, but I want to say that you should learn from those who can learn from. I would like to say that it is necessary to ensure the integral relationship between parents and society, for this we need to hold meetings with parents, we need to raise their morale and level, and in this, the role of society's institutions will certainly be important. At this point, I would like to draw your attention to one more idea, there is a famous proverb in our people, "Kars is a sword, and it comes out of two hands", and in many places we cannot help but recognize how true this idea is. Q. There is one aspect of the matter that I found necessary to mention here. We believe that not only parents are responsible for the above-mentioned problems, but also some shortcomings in our education system.

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